

Electronic States of Isomeric Hydroxybenzoic Acids and their Mono- and Di-anionic Species†

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Absorption and emission spectra of isomeric hydroxybenzoic acids in different solvents and at different pH values have been studied. The results have been supplemented by CNDO/S calculations. Their electronic states have been characterised. The acid-base equilibria in the ground and excited states have also been discussed.

THE photochemistry and photobiology of substituted benzenes has attracted attention of many groups of workers¹⁻⁶. For better understanding of their photochemical behaviour it is imperative that electronic states of these molecules are well characterised. No systematic and complete study⁷⁻⁹ has been reported so far on hydroxybenzoic acids. Here, we present in some details the electronic spectra of hydroxybenzoic acids under different experimental conditions as a part of our program¹⁰⁻¹² of systematic study of the electronic spectra of disubstituted benzenes. The concentration of benzoic acids have been so chosen as to avoid the formation of dimeric species which can lead to complication in the interpretation of the spectra.

Experimental

Solutions of hydroxybenzoic acids (B.D.H., AnalaR) in warm ethanol were treated with activated charcoal, filtered, cooled and kept aside to obtain hydroxybenzoic acids as crystalline solids. The crystals were washed with cold ethanol and dried under vacuum. Absolute ethanol for use as solvent, was twice distilled over sodium metal and stored over molecular sieves. Cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane¹³ were stirred with sulphuric acid, washed with water and dried over fused calcium chloride, and distilled twice over sodium metal. Acetonitrile was distilled over phosphorous pentoxide, and its middle fraction (b.p. 354 K) was used. Methanol (A.R. grade) was used as such. Water was triple-distilled over potassium dichromate and potassium permanganate solutions.

Absorption spectra were taken on a UV VIS-NIR Hitachi spectrophotometer. Oscillator strength f is calculated by using the relationship,

$$f = 4.32 \times 10^{-9} \epsilon_{\max} \Delta \bar{\nu}$$

where, $\epsilon_{\max}$ is the experimental extinction coefficient at band maximum and $\Delta \bar{\nu}$ is the half band width (in wave numbers). The fluorescence measurements

were made on a Perkin-Elmer MPF-44B spectrofluorimeter. Calculations were carried in the CNDO/S approximation of Del Bene and Jaffe^{14,15}, using the quantum chemistry program exchange (QCPE 174). Bond lengths and bond angles used in these calculations were taken from literature¹⁶. The molecular axes and number of atoms are designated in Fig. 1. The excited states were generated from the ground state occupied and virtual orbitals through a configuration interaction procedure between the forty lowest energy singly excited states. The characterisation of electronic

Fig. 1. Molecular axes designations of hydroxybenzoic acids, Y-axis is out of plane.

states have been made on the basis of configurational analysis. In order to study the intramolecular charge transfer in these states it is convenient to divide each hydroxybenzoic acid into the sub-systems $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ and $-\text{COOH}$. The charge on the various sub-systems have been obtained from the knowledge of electron densities on various atoms in the group. The electron densities on various atoms in the excited state j are given by.

$${}^j\rho_A = \rho_A^0 + \sum_m^{\text{CIA}} \sum_{\mu} C_{jm}^{\mu} (C_{\mu l}^{\mu} - C_{\mu i}^{\mu})$$

† Dedicated to Professor Sadhan Basu on the occasion of his 65th birthday.

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TABLE 1—ABSORPTION MAXIMA ($\bar{\nu}$, kK) OF ISOMERIC HYDROXYBENZOIC ACIDS IN VARIOUS SOLVENTS

Cyclohexane	Methylcyclohexane	Acetonitrile		Methanol		Ethanol	
$\bar{\nu}$	$\bar{\nu}$	$\bar{\nu}$	f	$\bar{\nu}$	f	$\bar{\nu}$	f
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzoate Acid							
32.05	32.47	32.79	0.585	33.00	0.257	32.89	0.189
41.67	42.02	42.37	0.338	42.55	0.369	42.55	0.404
46.30				47.61	0.508	47.40	0.886
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid							
33.00	33.11	33.89	0.055	33.67	0.090	33.67	0.119
42.74		42.73	0.140	42.55	0.246	42.74	0.372
47.39				47.39	0.561	46.51	0.515
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid							
		35.21	0.008	33.33	Shoulder	33.33	0.012
		39.63	0.789	39.37	0.408	39.22	0.637
				48.54	0.340	47.17	0.374

TABLE 2—ABSORPTION MAXIMA ($\bar{\nu}$, kK) OF ISOMERIC HYDROXYBENZOIC ACIDS AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH					
1 (neutral)		7 (monoanion)		>10 (dianion)	
$\bar{\nu}$	f	$\bar{\nu}$	f	$\bar{\nu}$	f
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid					
32.79	0.106	34.01	0.371	32.36*	0.102
42.02	0.157	43.48	0.499	41.49	0.171
49.02	0.931			43.86	0.133
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid					
33.78	0.087	34.84	0.126	31.95	0.061
42.01	0.148	43.48	0.467	41.15	0.162
43.08	0.574			45.87	0.520
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid					
39.06	0.657	35.46	0.043	35.46	0.490
48.31	0.421	40.65	0.443	46.08	0.168

* In 5 N KOH.

in which ρ_A^0 is the ground electron density on atom A and C_{jm} being the coefficient of the m th configuration contributing to the j th state. $C_{\mu f}$ and $C_{\mu i}$ are the orbital coefficients of the final and initial MO involved in the m th configuration. All calculations have been done on DEC 2050 machine.

Results and Discussion

Absorption spectra :

Neutral molecules : The absorption spectra of isomeric hydroxybenzoic acids were determined in various solvents. The $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ (in kK) values together with the oscillator strength (f) for these compounds are given in Tables 1 and 2. Due to the poor solubility of *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid in cyclohexane and methylcyclohexane the spectra could not be recorded even for the saturated solutions. The low energy absorption bands are blue-shifted with increase in the dielectric constant of polar solvents. However, this band is blue-shifted in methanol with respect to the spectra in acetonitrile for *o*-hydroxy-

benzoic acid whereas for *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acid a small red-shift is observed in going from acetonitrile to methanol. In aqueous solutions the spectra were recorded at $pH \sim 1$ to ensure that the acids are present mainly in neutral form.

Monoanions : In water the carboxylic group of these molecules gets deprotonated. It has been found that between pH 7 and 8 the absorption spectra (Table 2) correspond to the species $HOC_6H_4COO^-$. All the bands are shifted to higher frequency in the benzoate ions.

Dianions : At still higher pH the phenolic group also dissociates to give the anion $OC_6H_4COO^-$. For hydroxybenzoic acid, the dianion exists only in highly alkaline media (5 M KOH). The absorption spectra shift towards lower frequency side of the corresponding neutral molecules. This is possibly due to the participation of the lone pairs on hydroxyl oxygen and the carboxyl oxygens with the π -electron system of the benzene ring in the same plane.

TABLE 3—FLUORESCENCE MAXIMA ($\bar{\nu}$, kK) OF ISOMERIC HYDROXYBENZOIC ACIDS IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS AND AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

Hydroxybenzoic acid	Cyclohexane	Methylcyclohexane	Ethanol	Water		
				pH=1	pH=7	pH>11
<i>ortho</i> -	26.74-27.03	23.64	22.42-22.72	23.51-23.81 (23.66)	23.9	24.6*
<i>meta</i> -	30.67-31.45	30.03	28.74-29.90	27.80	24.60	24.6
<i>para</i> -	35.21-36.23	—	32.05-32.47	31.06-31.45 (31.25)	No fluorescence	29.9

* In 5 N KOH.

Emission spectra :

The emission bands for the hydroxybenzoic acids in different solvents and at different pH values are given in Table 3. It is apparent from Table 3 that significant red-shift in fluorescence occurs as the solvent polarity increases when compared to the spectrum in cyclohexane. This is indicative of increase in the dipole moment upon excitation. The behaviour of *o*-hydroxybenzoic acid is quite different from the *m*- and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids. Due to close vicinity of OH and COOH groups and decrease in the pK of OH dissociation and increase in pK of COOH dissociation, the formation of zwitterion¹⁷ in the excited state is possible.

Table 2 reveals that the mono- and di-anions of *meta*-isomer fluoresce at the same wavelength whereas the monoanion of *p*-HBA is non-fluorescent and the dianion of all isomers are strongly fluorescent. All the hydroxybenzoic acids show phosphorescence. The lowest triplet in EPA as solvent is observed at 24.55 in *ortho*-, 23.53 in *meta*- and 24.85 kK in case of *para*-hydroxybenzoic acids.

Theoretical results and their correlation with experimental data :

The theoretical values (after configuration interaction) are compared with the experimental results in cyclohexane (in methanol in the case of *p*-HBA) in Table 4. A number of theoretically predicted transitions for which oscillator strength is zero or small are not observed experimentally. The $S_0 \rightarrow S_2$ transition in all the isomeric hydroxybenzoic acids (mainly polarised along the short axis) has been assigned to the lowest observed band. The second experimentally observed band have been assigned to the theoretically predicted $S_0 \rightarrow S_5$ in *o*- and *p*-hydroxybenzoic acids and to $S_0 \rightarrow S_4$ in the case of *m*-hydroxybenzoic acid, which are polarised along the long axis of the benzene. The strongest absorption band at 46.30 kK in *o*-HBA and at 47.39 kK in *m*-HBA have been assigned to the $S_0 \rightarrow S_6$ and $S_0 \rightarrow S_5$ transitions, respectively. The agreement between the experimental and theoretical values of transition energies and other quantities seem to confirm the assignments.

Nature of the lowest excited state :

In benzoic acid and the lowest excited state is of $n\pi^*$ nature, however, in hydroxybenzoic acids the lone

TABLE 4—ELECTRONIC STATE OF HYDROXYBENZOIC ACIDS

Experimental $\bar{\nu}$ kK	Theoretical		Type
	$\bar{\nu}$ kK	<i>f</i>	
<i>o</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid			
32.05	24.58	0	$S_1 n\pi^*$
	35.26	0.040	$S_2 \pi\pi^*$
	40.16	0	$S_3 mix$
	41.16	0	$S_4 n\pi^*$
	43.80	0.042	$S_5 \pi\pi^*$
46.30	50.47	0.486	$S_6 mix$
<i>m</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid			
33.00	25.12	0	$S_1 n\pi^*$
	35.67	0.019	$S_2 \pi\pi^*$
	41.03	0	$S_3 n\pi^*$
	44.97	0	$S_4 mix$
47.39	50.86	0.502	$S_5 \pi\pi^*$
<i>p</i> -Hydroxybenzoic Acid			
33.33*	25.68	0	$S_1 n\pi^*$
	35.96	0.006	$S_2 mix$
	41.22	0	$S_3 \pi\pi^*$
	42.47	0	$S_4 \pi\pi^*$
	43.21	0.169	$S_5 mix$
48.54*	51.54	0.407	$S_6 mix$

* In methanol.

pair on oxygen of hydroxyl group is in conjugation with the π -electrons of benzene and this extended conjugation may lead to the energy of $\pi\pi^*$ transition nearly equal to or slightly lower than $n\pi^*$ transition energy. This is supported experimentally by the facts, (i) that the extinction coefficient of all the bands are quite large which cannot be due to $n\pi^*$ transition, (ii) that at room temperature fluorescence is generally observed if S_1 is a $\pi\pi^* \rightarrow \pi$, and phosphorescence if S_1 is $\pi^* \rightarrow n$ and (iii) that the observed solvent effect also support the nature of the transition to be $\pi\pi^*$. It is possible that the $n\pi^*$ transition ($S_0 \rightarrow S_1$) may be buried under the strong $\pi\pi^*$ band.

The fluorescence properties (Table 3) of the various anionic species are quite interesting. In the case of *o*-HBA both the mono- and di-anionic forms fluoresce and the $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ are well separated. For the *m*-HBA, both the mono- and di-anionic forms fluoresce at the same $\bar{\nu}_{max}$ value whereas the monoanionic form in the case of *para*-isomer is non-fluorescent and the dianionic form is fluorescent. This could be explained as follows :

It is well known that the acidity of the phenolic^{18,19} group increases tremendously in the singlet excited state. Thus, in the excited state the monoanion of *m*-HBA is converted into the dianion and the fluorescence data even at pH 7 correspond to that of dianions. This is further supported by the fluorescence data in the alkaline media. As mentioned earlier, the monoanion of *p*-HBA does not fluoresce whereas the dianion does. This clearly indicates the different behaviour of monoanions of *m*- and *p*-HBAs in the excited state, i.e. in the excited state monoanion of *m*-HBA is converted into the dianion and the monoanion of *p*-HBA is not converted into the dianion as the dianionic form is fluorescent. Possibly in the excited state, the phenolic hydrogen is transferred to the carboxylate ion inter-molecularly or intra-molecularly giving the

which might be having the lowest singlet state of $\pi\pi^*$ nature and is thus non-fluorescent. It is worth mentioning here that the determination of gaseous phase acidity of these molecules by Kabrle²⁰ indicate that for *p*-HBA in the gaseous state it is the phenolic hydrogen which dissociates first, preferentially over the carboxylic hydrogen. The theoretical INDO calculations²¹ on these molecules are also in agreement with our observations.

Acid-base equilibria :

The excited state pK_a values pK_a^* at room temperature for the equilibrium (I) and (II).

were calculated the Forster²² cycle method, i.e. $pK_a - pK_a^* = 2.3 \times 10^{-8} (\bar{\nu}_{\text{HA}} - \bar{\nu}_{\text{A}})$, where $\bar{\nu}_{\text{HA}}$ and $\bar{\nu}_{\text{A}}$ are the band maxima (cm^{-1}) of the acid and the conjugate base, respectively. The ground state pK_a values for the equilibrium (I) determined potentiometrically for the *o*-, *m*-, *p*-HBAs are respectively 3.00, 4.08 and 4.07, and the corresponding excited state pK_a^* (I) values calculated using the absorption data are found to be 5.56 and 6.31, respectively for the *o*- and *m*-HBA. The pK^* (I) and also pK^* (II) values for the *para*-isomer could not be calculated as the mono- and di-anionic species absorb at the same wavelength. The ground state pK_a (II) values for *o*-, *m*- and *p*-HBAs 10.82, 9.80 and 9.46 respectively, and the corresponding value for pK^* (II) are 10.35 and 3.73 for *o*- and *m*-HBAs. The pK^* values for equilibrium (I) are large compared to pK (I) and for equilibrium (II), pK^* (II) values are lower compared to pK_a (II) in the ground state. These are in agreement with the pK^* values reported for these type of equilibrium^{18,19}. For the pure $\pi\pi^*$

singlet state the electronic charge density on the carboxylic group (q_{COOH}) increases and a qualitative correlation exists between q_{COOH} and pK^* (I) (Table 5). The fluorescence data cannot be used for the determination of pK^* (I) and pK^* (II) for the reasons explained above.

TABLE 5 - GROUND AND EXCITED STATE CHARGE DENSITIES IN HYDROXYBENZOIC ACIDS

Compound	Sub-system	State		Remarks
		S_0	1L_b	
<i>o</i> -HBA	-OH	-0.106	0.098	$\pi\pi^*$
	-COOH	-0.001	-0.048	
	$-\phi-$	-0.011	-0.166	
<i>m</i> -HBA	-OH	-0.061	0.012	$\pi\pi^*$
	-COOH	-0.048	-0.108	
	$-\phi-$	-0.016	-0.080	
<i>p</i> -HBA	-OH	-0.059	0.010	Mixed
	-COOH	-0.059	0.087	
	$-\phi-$	-0.006	-0.056	

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